

THE ROLE OF *LANGHANA* ON MANAGEMENT OF LIFESTYLE DISORDERS AND ITS IMPACT ON MENTAL HEALTH

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ABSTRACT

Langhana is an important therapeutic principle in Ayurveda that aims to reduce bodily heaviness, eliminate metabolic toxins (*Ama*), and restore the balance of *Dosha* by enhancing digestive fire (*Agni*). It is indicated in conditions associated with impaired digestive, obstruction of body channels (*Srotorodha*), accumulation of *Ama*, and metabolic disorders. *Aacharya Charak* and *Aacharya Vagbhatt*, describe various types of *Langhana* including fasting (*Upavasa*), light diet (*Pachana*), physical exercise (*Vyayama*), exposure to sun and wind (*Atapa* and *Maruta*), thirst therapy (*Pipasa*), which are selected according to the patient's strength (*Bala*), disease severity (*Roga Bala*). *Langhana* promotes detoxification, improves digestion and metabolism, reduces excess *Kapha* and *Meda*, and enhances lightness and clarity in the body. Emerging scientific evidence also suggests beneficial effects of fasting on

metabolic health and mental well-being. Thus, *Langhana* represents a cost-effective, preventive, and therapeutic approach with significant relevance in lifestyle and metabolic disorders.

KEYWORDS: *Langhana*, *Ama*, *Agni*, Lifestyle disorders, Mental health.

INTRODUCTION

Langhana is one of the fundamental therapeutic principles in Ayurveda, primarily aimed at reducing heaviness and restoring metabolic balance in the body. The term *Langhana* literally means “to lighten”, and its includes therapeutic measures that decrease excess *Dosha*, eliminate metabolic toxins (*Ama*), and improve digestive fire (*Agni*). It is especially indicated in conditions associated with over- nourishment, impaired digestion, obstruction of body channels (*Srotorodha*), and accumulation of (*Kapha and Meda*). Various forms of *Langhana* such as fasting, light diet, physical exercise, controlled exposure to sun and wind. *Langhana* plays a vital role in both preventive and therapeutic health. *Langhana* also serve as a mental health enhancer.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

- Concept of *Langhana*.
- Detail study of *Langhana Upkarama* and management of lifestyle disorder through *Langhana*.
- Impact of *Langhana* on mental health.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- Various classical texts – (*Charak Samhita, Ashtanga Hridaya*, etc and their commentaries).
- Different research articles (google scholar, research gate).
- Various Sanskrit Hindi dictionaries.

Langhana Upkarama

Langhana means bringing lightness and thinness to the body. *Upkarama* means treatment.

“Yet Kinchit laghava karam Dehe Tallanghanam Smruta |”

(*Charaka Samhita Sutrasthana 22/9*)

The treatment that brings lightness lightness and thinness to the body is called *Langhana Upkarama*. It is also called a De-nourishing treatment.

“Langhanam laghavaya yat dehasya”

(*Ashtanga Hridaya Sutrasthana 14/2*)

In *Ashtanga Hridaya*, *Langhana* is defined as the therapy that lightens the body. In modern terminology, *Langhana* means fasting or caloric restriction.

Langhana Upkarama refers to therapeutic measures that induce lightness and reduction of heaviness in body. The term *Langhana* denotes the process of achieving lightness and thinness, while *Upkarama* signifies treatment.

Principle of *Langhana Upkarama*

“*Rogah sarve api mandeh aagnou sutaram udaradi tu*”

(*Ashtanga Hridaya Nidanasthana 12/1*)

According to Ayurveda, most diseases originate from the imbalance of Agni (digestive fire). In the state of *Mandagni*, ingested food is not digested properly and remains in an undigested form (*Apakva*), leading to the formation of *Ama* (metabolic toxins). *Ama* acts as primary etiological factor in the pathogenesis of several diseases by obstructing the channels (*Srotas*) of the body and there by contributing to the manifestation of various pathological conditions.

Enhancement of Agni

Clearance of channels

Detoxification of Ama

Elimination via sweat, respiration, urine and feces, etc

Types of Langhana

“*Chatusprakara Samsuddhi Pipasa Marutatapau*

Pachanam Upavasasca Vyayamasca Iti Langhanam”

(*Charak Samhita 22/18*)

“*Sodhanam Samanam Cheti Dvidha TrTrapi Langhanam*”

(*Ashtanga Hridaya Sutrasthana 14/4*)

Langhana

- *Shodhan*
- *Shaman*

<i>Ayurvedic Terms</i>	<i>English</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Primary Action</i>
<i>Samsodhana</i> (<i>Vaman, Virechan, Nasya, Nirubasti, Raktmokshan</i>)	Purificatory therapy	Bi-cleansing procedure to expel aggravated <i>Dosha</i>	Eliminates <i>Dosha</i> and <i>Ama</i>
<i>Pipasa</i>	Thirst therapy	Controlled with holding of fluids	Reduces <i>Kapha</i> , increase <i>Agni</i>
<i>Maruta</i>	Exposure to wind	Therapeutic exposure to fresh air	Induce lightness and dryness
<i>Atapa</i>	Exposure to sun	Sun therapy in controlled manner	Enhances metabolism
<i>Pachana</i>	Digestive therapy	Use of digestive measures to digest <i>Ama</i>	<i>Ama Pachana</i>
<i>Upavasa</i>	Fasting	Astinance from food for a specific period	Reduces digestive load
<i>Vyayama</i>	Physical exercise	Planned physical activities	Reduces <i>Meda</i> , enhance <i>Agni</i>

<i>Deepan</i>	Appetite/digestive therapy	Use of enhance Agni and digest <i>Ama</i>	Enhance Agni and <i>Ama Pachana</i>
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Type	Clinical Relevance
<i>Samsodhana</i>	Chronic metabolic disorders, obesity, <i>Kapha -Pitta</i> dominance
<i>Pipasa</i>	Heaviness, fluids retention
<i>Maruta</i>	<i>Kapha</i> disorders
<i>Atapa</i>	<i>Kapha -Meda</i> disorders
<i>Pachana</i>	Indigestion, metabolic toxins
<i>Upavasa</i>	Obesity, <i>Ama</i> , <i>Mandagni</i>
<i>Vyayama</i>	Obesity, sedentary lifestyle disorders
<i>Deepan</i>	Indigestion, <i>Ama</i> , <i>Mandagni</i>

The specific type of *Langhana* method is used depending upon the patient's *Bala* (strength), *Roga Bala* (severity of disease), season and appropriate time (*Kala*). Proper assessment of these factors helps in choosing the most suitable *Langhana* method, ensuring safety and better therapeutic outcomes for the patient.

Characteristics feature of *Langhana Dravya*

“*Laghu Ushna Teekshna Vishadam Rukshma Sukshma Kharam Saram* /

Katheenam Ch Aevam Yatt Dravyam Prayaha Tat Langhanm Smrutam // (*Charaka Samhita Sutrasthana 22/12*)”

- *Laghu* (light)
- *Ushna* (hot)
- *Teekshna* (sharp)
- *Vishada* (non-slimy) – removal of adhesiveness
- *Rooksha* (dry) – brings lightness to the body
- *Sookshma* (minute) – that enter in minutest body channels
- *Khara* (rough)- clear the body channels
- *Sara* (mobility)- removal of toxin in body
- *Katina* (hardness)

Indication of *Langhana* in lifestyle disease

- Diseases in which heaviness take place. E.g- Diabetes mellitus, obesity, fever and indigestion.
- Diseases in which obstruction of channels take place. E.g- Asthma, hyperlipidemias coronary artery disease, constipation.

Condition	Ayurvedic Perspective
<i>Kapha dominant disorders</i>	Heaviness (<i>Gaurava</i>), lethargy (<i>Alasya</i>), excess mucus, congestion
<i>Meda Dushti/obesity (Adipopathy)</i>	Excess adipose tissue, obesity metabolic sluggishness
<i>Mandagni</i>	Diminished digestive fire with indigestion and poor appetite
<i>Ama dominant condition</i>	Coated tongue, heaviness, bloating, nausea
<i>Santarpanajanya vyadhi</i>	Diseases due to over-nourishment (e.g., <i>Prameha</i> , <i>Sthaulya</i>)
<i>Jwara (early stage)</i>	Fever associated with <i>Ama</i> and <i>Kapha</i> predominance
<i>Ajeerna</i>	Indigestion, fullness, abdominal discomfort
<i>Lifestyle disorders</i>	Sedentary lifestyle, dyslipidemia, metabolic syndrome (supportive role)

Contraindication

<i>Karshya</i>	Malnutrition
<i>Daurbalya</i>	General weakness, fatigue
<i>Vata</i> - predominant conditions	Excess dryness, anxiety, tremors
Pregnancy	Increased nutritional requirement for mother and fetus
Lactation	Risk of reduced milk production
Children and Elderly	Increased risk of disability
Chronic diseases	Tuberculosis, malignancy, chronic disorders
Acute dehydration	Severe thirst, electrolyte imbalance
Post therapy weakness	After shodhan or major illness
Severe anemia	Risk weakness and fatigue

Characteristics feature of appropriate *Langhana Chikitsa/Therapy*

“*Vat Mutra Pureeshanam Visarge GatraLaghava |Hrudaya Udgara Kanthassya Shudhhau Tandra Klame Gate ||*”

(*charak samhita Sutrasthana 22/34*)

“*Swede Jate Ruchau Chaiv Kshut Pipas Sah Udaye |Krutanam Langhanam Aadeshyam Nivayarthe ch Antaratmanee||*”

(*Charaka Samhita Sutrasthana 22/35*)

Langhana is properly administrated, the person experiences lightness in the body, clarity of mind and senses, purification of the heart and mouth, reduction of heaviness and fatigue, proper elimination of urine and feces, and a pleasant feeling of well-being. Hunger and thirst appear in a balanced manner, digestion become proper, and the body feels free from obstruction. These features indicate the successful action of *Langhana* therapy.

Impact of *Langhana* on mental health

Langhana (fasting or lightening therapy) plays a vital role in Ayurveda by enhancing digestive fire (*Agni*), eliminating toxins (*Ama*), and clearing body channels (*Srotas*), thereby promoting lightness and improve metabolism. Proper digestion and assimilation of food after *Langhana* contribute to the better physical health, which is closely linked to the mental well-being.

Scientific observations also support that fasting can improve mood, reduce anxiety and depression and enhance overall psychological functioning through neurobiological mechanisms such as changes in neurotransmitters and improved sleep quality.

Many clinical observations relate an early effect of fasting on depressive symptoms with an improvement in mood, alertness and a sense of peacefulness. Thus, fasting serves as a mental health enhancer.

Good physical health positively influences mental health. In Ayurveda, it is understood that mental health also influences physical health. Therefore, both physical and mental health are interrelated and should be addressed together for overall well-being.

CONCLUSION

In the modern era, there is a significant increase in lifestyle disorders and mental stress. People, especially the youth, are highly influenced by junk food and consume *Viruddha Ahara* (incompatible food) in their daily life. This leads to an increase in lifestyle disorders and promotes a sedentary lifestyle, which disturbs the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) and further increases the incidence of life style-related diseases. These activities affect not only physical health but also mental health.

They cause imbalance of the body *Doshas* and disturb *Agni* (digestive fire). *Langhana* represents a cost-effective, preventive and therapeutic approach.

SUMMARY

Langhana, which includes fasting and lightening therapies, plays an important role in maintaining physical and mental health by improving digestion, metabolism, and elimination of toxins (*Ama*). It helps balance *Agni* (digestive fire) and *Doshas*, thereby supporting proper functioning of body systems. By reducing the load on the digestive systems, *Langhana* enhances nutrient absorption and promotes detoxification. The practice is beneficial in

lifestyle disorders caused by the sedentary habits, overeating, and consumption of incompatible foods. Additionally, *Langhana* contributes to mental well-being by improving mood, reducing stress, and enhancing clarity and alertness. Regular and appropriate application of *Langhana* can support weight management, improve sleep quality, and boost overall vitality. Thus, *Langhana* serves as a simple, cost-effective, preventive, and therapeutic approach in Ayurveda for promoting holistic health and preventing lifestyle related diseases.

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